

New flat-fan sheets adiabatic absorber for direct air-cooled LiBr/H₂O absorption machines: Simulation, parametric study and experimental results

A. González-Gil^{a,b,e}, M. Izquierdo^{a,b,e}, J.D. Marcos^c, E. Palacios^d

^a Instituto de Ciencias de la Construcción Eduardo Torroja (CSIC), c/Serrano Galvache 4, 28033 Madrid, Spain

^b Escuela Politécnica Superior, UC3M, Avenida de la Universidad 30, 28911 Leganés, Madrid, Spain

^c Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería Industrial, UNED, c/Juan del Rosal 12, 28040 Madrid, Spain

^d Escuela Universitaria de Ingeniería Técnica Industrial, UPM, c/Ronda de Valencia 3, 28012 Madrid, Spain

^e Unidad de Asociada de Ingeniería de Sistemas Energéticos CSIC-UC3M, Spain

Corresponding author at: Instituto de Ciencias de la Construcción Eduardo Torroja (CSIC), c/Serrano Galvache 4, 28033 Madrid, Spain. Tel./fax: +34 918713248.

E-mail address: arturogzgil@gmail.com (A. González-Gil).

Abstract

A new generation of highly efficient absorbers for direct air-cooled LiBr/H₂O absorption machines is presented and discussed in this paper. As distinguishing aspects of these absorbers, it is worth mentioning that they are adiabatic units, which improves the heat and mass transfer; besides, they distribute the solution in flat-fan sheets, which allows for compact absorber designs; lastly, they are directly air-cooled units, which eliminates the need of cooling towers. Additionally, the paper includes the development of a mathematical modeling for analysis and simulation of this kind of absorbers. Based on that model, a parametric study of the proposed absorber design is carried out to optimize its use in a particular air-cooled single–double-effect absorption machine. Simulation outcomes of that specific absorber were compared with some experimental results obtained by using the aforementioned absorption machine as testing facility to validate the model. A good agreement was found between predictions and experimental results for most of the characteristic operation parameters of the absorber. Finally, it was observed that the proposed absorber design enables air-cooled LiBr/H₂O absorption machines to work far from crystallization limits even at ambient temperatures around 40 °C.

Keywords: Absorption, Lithium bromide, Adiabatic absorber, Direct air-cooled, Modeling, experimental validation

1. Introduction

Absorption technologies for air-conditioning in buildings have been receiving growing attention for the last years. In this sense, water-cooled absorption chillers seem to be a very attractive option to replace conventional electrically driven systems in large installations, as reported by [1] or [2]. In turn, the use of air-cooled absorption machines is generally preferred for low capacity applications, as stated, for instance, in [3]. As compared to water-cooled systems, they do not need a cooling tower to remove the heat from condensation and absorption processes, but they use the surrounding air as a free coolant. Consequently, both the installation and operational costs are lower and, what is more, health problems such as Legionella are avoided. Furthermore, the lack of water consumption makes air-cooled machines very adequate for regions where this source is a precious commodity. However, in spite of all those advantages, currently in the market one cannot find any air-cooled absorption chiller. The last air-cooled LiBr/H₂O absorption chiller marketed was the *Rotartica 045v*, which consisted of a single-effect machine indirectly air-cooled (re-cooling) designed to work with solar energy, see for instance [4] or [5]. However, it is interesting to note that, since the manufacturing company went bankrupt a few years ago, that chiller is no longer available in the market.

On the other hand, LiBr/H₂O solution is regarded as one of the most interesting working fluids for absorption chillers because of its high performance, see [6] or [7]. However, a relatively high risk of solution crystallization appears in working at high absorption temperatures, as reported by [8] or [9]. Due to the heat transfer limitations of air as cooling source, air-cooled absorbers normally operate at higher temperatures than water-cooled ones and, as a result, solution is forced to work riskily closer to crystallization limits. Nowadays, this is regarded as a major obstacle

for commercialization of air-cooled absorption machines based on LiBr/H₂O.

Even though in the literature there are only a few publications about air-cooled absorption machines, one can find some interesting works reporting on possible solutions to overcome the crystallization problem. Some of them are investigations on new salt mixtures that do not crystallize in such working conditions, see for instance [10–12] or [13]. Other reports like [14] or [15] analyzed new configurations for falling film absorbers, traditionally used with water-cooled technology; however, the main problems associated with falling film type absorbers could not be solved: low mass transfer, low heat transfer and large volume. Alternatively, a new control strategy based on increasing the chilled water temperature was proposed by [16]. Lastly, the use of lower driving temperature was proposed as a different option to develop air-cooled LiBr/H₂O absorption chillers, [17].

In spite of the fact that the above exposed options seem to be adequate to solve the crystallization problems in air-cooled absorption machines, they are either complex to implement or reduce the performance of LiBr/H₂O cycles. Besides, those alternatives do not contribute to reducing size of absorbers, which is also regarded as a major barrier for commercialization of low capacity absorption chillers. In this sense, the utilization of a hydrophobic membrane contactor at the liquid–vapor interface was proposed as a possible solution to obtain compact absorbers for LiBr/H₂O absorption chillers, [18]. However, the use of this promising innovation has not been tested in air-cooled systems yet. In contrast, the utilization of adiabatic absorbers looks like a valid choice to reduce the risk of crystallization and to keep the operation of LiBr/H₂O absorption cycles simple. Additionally, adiabatic absorbers allow for a considerably reduction in the size of absorption chillers, as pointed out in different publications such as [19]. Unlike traditional falling film absorbers, in adiabatic absorbers heat and mass processes are separated. Absorption of the evaporated refrigerant takes place in an adiabatic chamber while the absorption heat is removed from the solution in a separate heat exchanger. Note that by facing the mass and heat transfer problems separately, higher improvements in both processes can be achieved.

With the aim of achieving compact absorption chambers in adiabatic absorbers, different configurations for the solution distribution have been proposed. To begin with, some authors like [20] or [21] suggested the solution atomization to increase the vapor-solution interface area and therefore enhance the absorption process. The spray absorber developed and patented by Ryan [20] presented the following drawbacks, according to the inventor himself flow liquid flow rates, calling for many sprayers and great absorber volumes; variable droplet diameter and significant proportion of droplets under 150 μm, which means that a considerable part of the pumped solution is of no use for absorption purpose; important head loss and high pumping consumption. Aiming at solving these problems, a new spray absorber with 400-μm diameter was proposed by [21]. This new approach was reported to deliver high mass transfer than Ryan's spray and multiplied the performance of commercial falling film absorbers by about fourfold.

However, in [22] it was reported that energy consumed in those spray absorbers is relatively high. The authors of that paper experimentally proved that films falling along sloping ramps is a more adequate configuration as any artificially generated pressure difference is needed, but it requires large absorption chambers. In [23] it was reported that conical liquid sheets can considerably scale down the absorber chambers, nevertheless, at the cost of consuming about 5 or 6 kJ of mechanical energy per kg of absorbed vapor. Lastly, the experimental investigation carried out in [24] demonstrated flat-fan sheets configuration performs better than falling film and spray absorbers. Thus, it was reported that this configuration allows for mass transfer coefficients about five times greater than the Warnakulasuriya and Worekx proposal [21]. Besides, although the rate of vapor absorbed per absorption chamber volume is slightly lower than for conical sheets, the energy demanded is much lower, around 1.5 kJ per kg of absorbed vapor.

To summarize, the use of flat-fan sheet sprayers can be regarded as a very adequate configuration for LiBr/H₂O air-cooled adiabatic absorbers. It enables a reasonably high rate of vapor absorption per chamber volume and, what is more, with a comparatively low demand of mechanical energy. On these grounds, the “Energy Saving and Emissions Reduction in Buildings” research group, sponsored by the Eduardo Torroja Institute for Construction Science (CSIC), patented a new absorber-evaporator assembly to efficiently operate at air-cooling conditions with LiBr/H₂O, [25]. It essentially consists of an adiabatic absorber with flat-fan sheets configuration which is assembled together with a falling film evaporator.

In the present work, the design of the aforementioned air-cooled adiabatic absorber with flat-fan sheets is

presented and discussed. Besides, the paper develops a mathematical model for analysis and simulation of that kind of absorbers. According to that model, a parametric study of the proposed absorber design is performed to optimize its application in a single-double-effect absorption prototype. Furthermore, some experimental parameters of the absorber operating in that machine are shown and compared with simulation results. As far as we know, in the literature there is not any similar work describing, simulating and testing complete flat-fan sheets adiabatic absorbers for air-cooled LiBr/ H₂O chillers.

2. Description of the absorber

Fig. 1 shows a schematic representation of the adiabatic absorber presented in this paper. As seen, the proposed design is suitable for single- or double-effect absorption machines directly cooled by air. In the same manner, this absorber design may be integrated into single-double-effect absorption machines such as the chiller described in [26].

The absorber assembly is essentially made up by a reservoir to store the diluted solution, a bank of flat-fan sheet sprayers, a solution gear pump (SP) and an air-cooling system to cool the solution. Additionally, it comprises three sprayers through which the concentrated solution coming from the generators enters the absorber. One of these sprayers is for the return of the single-effect generator (point 3 in Fig. 1) while the other two are for the returns of the high- and low-pressure generators, in case of double-effect operation (4 and 5, respectively).

The air-cooling system assembled to remove the heat generated in the vapor absorption process is essentially formed by a recirculation solution pump (RSP), a solution air-cooler and a fan. The diluted and warmed solution (1) is pumped by a magnetically driven gear pump through the heat exchanger (m_{sac}), where it is directly cooled by the outdoor air (6 and 7 for the solution; 8 and 9 for the air flow). Once cooled (7), the solution returns to the absorber reservoir through a series of flat-fan sheet sprayers, considerably contributing to the absorption of the vapor coming from the evaporator, (m_v). Finally, part of the solution in the reservoir (m_s) is pumped to the generator/s (2), thus completing the LiBr/H₂O solution cycle.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the prototype's absorber

Regarding the solution air-cooler integrated in the adiabatic absorber, it is formed by two identical finned-tube heat exchangers installed in parallel circuits. These circuits were designed in such a way that the solution mass flow rates through each of them is roughly the same; that is, $m_{sac}/2$. As for the solution mass flow rate through each injector nozzle in the bank of sprayers, from (24) it can be drawn that 100 kg/h provides the highest vapor absorption rate with the minimum pressure drop, or what is the same, with the lowest consumption of mechanical energy. Besides, the authors of that paper concluded that 200 mm is an adequate length for the absorption chamber since the absorption process is nearly finished at this point. In this sense, it was reported that around 90% of the sheet absorption capacity is achieved in the first 200 mm. The number of sprayers in the absorber chamber and the air flow rate through the solution air-cooler will be determined after the parametric study exposed below.

On the other hand, it is notable that the proposed design enables to assemble the absorber and the evaporator together in the same chamber. In this way, the water vapor generated in the evaporator is directly absorbed by the

solution in the absorber. The lack of piping between these two components significantly reduces the pressure drop and consequently improves the absorption process.

3. Analytical model

The model proposed in this paper to simulate direct air-cooled adiabatic absorbers with flat-fan sheets essentially consists of two substructures: one for describing the vapor absorption process taking place in the absorption chamber (Sections 3.1 and 3.2); the other one for modeling the solution air-cooler (Section 3.3). An energy balance of the whole absorber using results from those subroutines completes the mathematical model of the absorber (Section 3.4). Fig. 2 shows a schematic representation of the model structure.

3.1. Mathematical model of vapor absorption into a single LiBr/H₂O flat-fan sheet

In the literature, one can find a large number of models for simulation of vapor absorption into falling films of aqueous lithium bromide solutions. In contrast, as far as we know, there is only one paper developing a model for flat-fan sheets, [27]. In that publication, a detailed formulation describing the non-isothermal absorption of vapor into freely expanding liquid sheets is provided, including different liquid flow configurations such as conical, disk and flat-fan. In spite of the fact that an experimental validation of the model was not given in that paper, in principle it was assumed as a valid methodology for numerical simulation of vapor absorption into single flat-fan sheets.

From implementation of that mathematical model, the maximum rate of vapor absorbed into every single LiBr/H₂O flat-fan sheet in the absorber may be calculated: $(\dot{m}_{v, \text{sheet}})_{\text{max}}$ for each sheet in the bank of sprayers; $(\dot{m}_{v, \text{g}})_{\text{max}}$ for the sheet formed at the return of the single-effect generator; $(\dot{m}_{v, \text{HG}})_{\text{max}}$ and $(\dot{m}_{v, \text{LG}})_{\text{max}}$ for the sheets formed at the returns of the high- and low-pressure generators, respectively (double-effect mode).

3.2. Modeling of vapor absorption in the adiabatic absorber

Regarding the modeling of the vapor absorption process in the whole absorber chamber, the following considerations were taken into account:

- Steady state conditions.
- Water vapor is the only gaseous substance in the absorption
- The absorption pressure is assumed to be constant though the entire chamber
- The bank of sprayers consists of a series of injectors that produce solution flat-fan sheets with identical properties: solution mass flow rate, sheet length, aperture angle initial concentration and initial temperature.
- It is assumed that the length of the sheets formed at each generator return is the same as for the sheets in the bank of sprayers; that is 200 mm.

As the absorption capacity determines the cooling power of any absorption chiller, the first step consists of calculating the maximum amount of water vapor that may be absorbed by the group of LiBr/H₂O flat-fan sheets in the absorber, $(\dot{m}_v)_{\text{max}}$.

According to the above assumptions, it is possible to state that all the solution sheets in the bank of sprayers have the same absorption potential. Thus, the following expression can be written to assess the maximum rate of vapor absorbed by all the sheets forming the bank of sprayers.

$$(\dot{m}_{v, \text{bank}})_{\text{max}} = n_{\text{sheet}} \cdot (\dot{m}_{v, \text{sheet}})_{\text{max}} \quad (1)$$

where n_{sheet} represents the number of solution sheets in the bank of sprayers.

The absorption capacity in the single-effect operation mode of the absorber will be given by

$$(\dot{m}_v)_{\text{max}} = (\dot{m}_{v, \text{bank}})_{\text{max}} + (\dot{m}_{v, \text{g}})_{\text{max}} \quad (2)$$

whereas for the double-effect stage it can be expressed as

$$(\dot{m}_v)_{\text{max}} = (\dot{m}_{v, \text{bank}})_{\text{max}} + (\dot{m}_{v, \text{HG}})_{\text{max}} + (\dot{m}_{v, \text{LG}})_{\text{max}} \quad (3)$$

Once the absorption capacity of the absorber is determined, it must be compared with the demanded vapor rate, $\dot{m}_{v, \text{abs}}$, which is a function of the cooling requirements of the machine, Q_e . If the value of $\dot{m}_{v, \text{abs}}$ is equal or lower than $(\dot{m}_v)_{\text{max}}$ then it can be affirmed that the cooling requirements may be met. Naturally, for this it will be necessary that the machine is able to generate the required refrigerant. In turn, if $\dot{m}_{v, \text{abs}}$ is higher than $(\dot{m}_v)_{\text{max}}$ it will not be possible to

produce the desired cooling effect because of absorber limitations. In that case, the maximum cooling capacity of the machine will be denoted as $Q_{e,max}$.

When considering the single-effect operation mode, the amount of vapor absorbed into the sheet of the generator return is given by

$$\dot{m}_{v,g} = \frac{(\dot{m}_{v,g})_{max}}{(\dot{m}_v)_{max}} \cdot \dot{m}_{v,abs} \quad (4)$$

In the same way, for the double-effect operation mode it can be written that

$$\dot{m}_{v,HG} = \frac{(\dot{m}_{v,HG})_{max}}{(\dot{m}_v)_{max}} \cdot \dot{m}_{v,abs} \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{m}_{v,LG} = \frac{(\dot{m}_{v,LG})_{max}}{(\dot{m}_v)_{max}} \cdot \dot{m}_{v,abs} \quad (6)$$

In turn, the vapor absorbed into each sheet of the bank of sprayers is given by

$$\dot{m}_{v,sheet} = \frac{(\dot{m}_{v,sheet})_{max}}{(\dot{m}_v)_{max}} \cdot \dot{m}_{v,abs} \quad (7)$$

In knowing the actual rate of vapor absorbed by every flat-fan sheet present in the absorber chamber, it is possible to ascertain some interesting parameters at their final positions, namely: solution temperature, solution mass fraction, approach to equilibrium factor or mean mass transfer coefficient. If taking, for instance, one single sheet in the bank of sprayers, the temperature at its final position ($T_{f,sheet}$) can be obtained from the following energy balance

$$(\dot{m}_v \cdot h_{abs})_{sheet} = \dot{m}_{s,sheet} \cdot C_{p,s} \cdot (T_f - T_i)_{sheet} \quad (8)$$

where $\dot{m}_{s,sheet}$ is the solution mass flow rate through each injector and h_{abs} is the specific heat of absorption. According to [22], the approach to equilibrium factor for a sheet in the bank of sprayers may be written as

$$F_{sheet} = \left(\frac{X_f - X_i}{X_{\infty} - X_i} \right)_{sheet} \approx \left(\frac{T_f - T_i}{T_{\infty} - T_i} \right)_{sheet} \quad (9)$$

In knowing T_f from Eq. (8), F_{sheet} is obtained and then, the solution mass fraction at the end of the sheet (X_f) can be calculated by using Eq. (9).

The mean mass transfer coefficient in the considered sheet, $h_{m,sheet}$, is obtained from the following expression, utilized in several studies such as [22] or [23].

$$\dot{m}_{v,sheet} = (\overline{h_m} \cdot A \cdot \overline{\Delta\rho})_{sheet} \approx (\overline{h_m} \cdot A \cdot \rho_i \cdot \Delta X_{lm})_{sheet} \quad (10)$$

where ΔX_{lm} is the logarithmic mean mass fraction difference and A_{sheet} represents the solution sheet area, which is a function of both its sheet length and its aperture angle θ . The value of θ depends on the solution mass flow through the nozzle injector and can be taken from [24].

Lastly, the subcooling is calculated as the difference between the equilibrium temperature of the solution at the beginning of the considered sheet and the actual temperature of the solution at that position in the following equation:

$$\Delta T_{sub} = T_{eq}(X_i) - T_i \quad (11)$$

Needless to say that expressions from Eqs. (8)–(11) are valid to obtain the parameters corresponding to any liquid flat-fan sheet in the absorber.

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the absorber modeling.

3.3 Modeling of the solution air-cooler

As earlier mentioned, the solution air-cooler of the adiabatic absorber consists of two identical finned-tube heat exchangers installed in parallel circuits. Besides, the system incorporates a fan to move the outdoor air through those heat exchangers. Classical heat transfer equations from [28] were used to model this aircooling system.

Regarding the pressure loss in the solution circuit of the absorber cooler (ΔP_{sac}), it is the result of adding the pressure drop in the bank of sprayers and the pressure drop through the pipes of the heat exchanger. Considering that injectors are set up in parallel configuration, the pressure loss in the bank of sprayers (ΔP_{bank}) is the same as for a single spray. In this sense, from [24] it is drawn that a pressure loss of 25 kPa is expected for the selected solution mass flow rate (100 kg/h). The pressure drop through the pipes of the heat exchanger (ΔP_{pipes}) is obtained from the *Darcy-Weisbach* correlation, taking account of valves and pipe elbows in the circuit. The energy consumption of the recirculation solution pump is calculated by the following equation:

$$W_{rsp} = \Delta P_{sac} \cdot \frac{\dot{m}_{sac}}{\eta_{rsp} \cdot \rho_s} \quad (12)$$

where η_{rsp} refers to the efficiency of the recirculation solution pump. It is taken as 0.5 in the present study.

The pressure drop suffered by the air through the external side of the heat exchanger (ΔP_{air}) is obtained according to conventional equations taking account of the fins effect, [28] and [29]. Eq. (13) gives the energy consumed by the fan, which is assumed to have an efficiency of $\eta_{fan} = 0.5$.

$$W_{fan} = \Delta P_{air} \cdot \frac{\dot{m}_{air}}{\eta_{fan} \cdot \rho_{air}} \quad (13)$$

Lastly, the energy consumption associated with the absorber operation (W_a) is the result of adding the consumptions of the recirculation pump (W_{rsp}) and the fan (W_{fan}).

3.4. Energy balance in the air-cooled adiabatic absorber

As above mentioned, the parallel circuits forming the absorber cooler are supposed to present the same pressure losses. Thus, taking into account the state points indicated in Fig. 1, the following energy balance can be written for each of the solution-air heat exchangers.

$$Q_{ac} = \frac{1}{2} \dot{m}_{sac} \cdot C_{p,s} \cdot (T_6 - T_7) \quad (14)$$

with $T_6 \approx T_1$

In turn, regarding the air side of the heat exchangers the energy balance can be expressed as

$$Q_{ac} = \frac{1}{2} \dot{m}_{air} \cdot C_{p,air} \cdot (T_9 - T_8) \quad (15)$$

where T_8 represents the ambient temperature, T_{out} .

If m_{sac} and m_{air} are defined as operation parameters of an absorption machine and both the outdoor temperature and the solution temperature in the solution reservoir are known, it is possible to ascertain the heat transfer rate and the outlet temperature of the two fluid flows; that is Q_{ac} , T_7 and T_9 . The *effectiveness-NTU* method was followed to perform those calculations [28].

On the other hand, according to the methodology shown in Section 3.2, the heat transferred to the solution during the vapor absorption process, Q_{abs} , can be expressed as

$$Q_{abs} = \sum_{i=1}^n \dot{m}_v \cdot h_{abs} \quad (16)$$

where n represents the total number of solution flat-fan sheets in the absorber.

Thus, considering the single-effect operation mode, an energy balance in the absorber assembly yields.

$$Q_{abs} + (\dot{m}_s - \dot{m}_v)h_3 - \dot{m}_s h_2 - 2Q_{ac} = m_1 C_{p,s} \frac{dT_1}{dt} \quad (17)$$

For the energy balance corresponding to the double-effect stage, the equation is equivalent. just taking account of the solution properties at the returns of both high- and low-pressure generators; that is:

$$Q_{abs} + (\dot{m}_{s,HG} - \dot{m}_{v,HG})h_4 + (\dot{m}_{s,LG} - \dot{m}_{v,LG})h_5 - \dot{m}_s h_2 - 2Q_{ac} = m_1 C_{p,s} \frac{dT_1}{dt} \quad (18)$$

with $m_s = m_{s,HG} + m_{s,IC}$ and $m_v = m_{v,HG} + m_{v,IC}$

Note that Eqs. (17) and (18) allow us to predict how the solution temperature in the absorber's reservoir varies with time.

4. Parametric study of the absorber design

In this section, the above exposed model will be used to optimize the design of a specific adiabatic absorber for single-double-effect absorption machines. Assuming a fixed geometry for the solution air heat exchangers (note that it is limited by the final dimensions of the given absorption machine), this analysis aims at determining the most adequate number of sprayers in the absorption chamber and specifying the optimum air flow rate through the absorber cooling system. The following considerations were taken into account:

- The analysis is carried out for an outdoor temperature of 35 °C.
- The solution mass flow through each sprayer is kept constant at 100kg/h.
- The air mass flow through the solution-air heat exchanger is varied from 1 to 5 kg/s.
- Input parameters for the absorber simulation such as evaporation temperature or solution concentration at the beginning of the sheets are obtained from a previous simulation of the absorption cycle, based on [30].

4.1. Results for the single-effect operation mode

Fig. 3 shows the variation of the UA coefficient in the absorber air-cooler with the number of sheets and the air flow rate. As seen, UA is higher when considering more sprayers in the absorber and when increasing the air flow rate. As well known, heat transfer is enhanced with higher flow rates. Moreover, it is observed from Fig. 3 that the influence of the solution flow in UA is less marked as the number of sheets grows. In fact, it may be stated that the

heat transfer improvement is noticeably less significant when exceeding around 20 sprayers. Likewise, the improvement achieved by varying the air flow rate seems to be less important at higher rates. For instance, whereas a mean enhancement of about 180% is reached by changing the air flow rate from 1 to 3 kg/s, it is just 60% when varying the flow from 3 to 5 kg/s.

Fig. 3. UA coefficient in the solution air-cooler of the absorber.

The effect of fluid flows variations on the solution temperature at the exit of the absorber air-cooler is represented in Fig. 4. It is seen that, even though an increase in the solution flow rate enhances the global heat transfer coefficient, the solution temperature at the exit of the heat exchangers raises with the number of sheets. This fact shows that the influence of having higher solution flow rates is more significant than the heat transfer enhancement. However, this negative effect may be mitigated by increasing the air mass flow rate through the heat exchangers.

Fig. 4. Solution temperatures at the outlet of the absorber air-cooler.

In Fig. 5, the influence of the studied parameters on the absorption potential of each liquid sheet is depicted. Since the amount of vapor absorbed is directly related to the solution subcooling, and therefore to the solution temperature at the outlet of the absorber air-cooler, it is clearly understandable that higher air flow rates yield greater absorption capacities. Likewise, the absorption potential is lower when increasing the number of sheets because higher solution flow rates circulate inside the heat exchangers. As in the previous case, the influence of the number of sheets seems to be less significant at higher air flow rates.

In Fig. 6, it is seen the variation of the absorber capacity as a function of the number of sheets and the air flow rate.

First, it is interesting to notice that, although the total absorption capacity of the absorber increases by adding sprayers, the improvement tends to be lower as the number of sprayers is higher. For instance, if taking an air flow rate of 1.5 kg/s and considering 20 sheets, the cooling power of a hypothetical prototype might be 4.3 kW as the maximum. In contrast, by selecting 30 sprayers and the same air flow rate, the maximum capacity of the absorber would be 5.1 kW, which represents an enhancement of just about 20%. Nonetheless, this effect is less marked when considering higher air flow rates. On the other hand, it is clearly seen in Fig. 6 that the absorber may improve its capacity by increasing the air flow rate through the external solution air-cooler. However, it is observed that the benefit achieved is less significant at higher rates.

Fig. 5. Vapor absorption potential of a single solution sheet.

Fig. 6. Maximum cooling capacity provided by the absorber in single-effect operation mode.

Regarding the energy consumed in the absorber, Fig. 7 shows how the pump consumption varies with the number of sprayers and Fig. 8 depicts the effect of the air flow rate on the fan consumption. Furthermore, in Fig. 9 the total consumption of both devices is plotted as a function of the number of solution sheets and the air flow rate. It is seen that, whereas an increment in the number of sheets barely affects the total consumption, the air flow rate has a strong influence. This is due to the fact that, while the energy consumed by the pump is directly proportional to the solution mass flow rate, the consumption of the fan is a quadratic function of the air flow rate.

Fig. 10 shows the ratio between the potential cooling capacity given by the absorber and the associated energy consumption (fan and recirculation pump). As seen, the ratio is considerably lower at higher air flow rates. Besides it is observed that, for intermediate air flow rates (1.5-3 kg/s) the ratio grows less significantly when exceeding around 15-20 sheets.

Fig. 7. Consumption of the recirculation solution pump depending upon the number of sheets

Fig. 8. Consumption of the fan depending upon the air flow rate.

Fig. 9. Power consumption of both the recirculation pump and the fan.

Fig. 10. Ratio of cooling capacity to energy consumption in the absorber.

4.2. Results for the double-effect operation mode

A similar analysis was performed for the double-effect operation mode of the absorber. To the authors' thought, presentation and discussion of all the obtained results might be redundant, so they were avoided. Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning that with 18 injectors in the bank of sprayers and 2.2 kg/s as air flow rate, around 7 kW of cooling capacity may be achieved with a reasonably low power consumption at ambient temperatures of 35 °C. Fig. 11 shows the capacity of the absorber as a function of the air flow rate and the number of sprayers.

Fig. 11. Maximum cooling capacity provided by the absorber in double-effect operation mode.

4.3. Conclusion of the parametric analysis

In view of the above results, it can be stated that installing 18 sprayers is a good option to obtain a good ratio between absorption capacity and energy consumption, both for single- and double-effect operation modes. Regarding the air flow rate through the solution air-cooler, it can be concluded that 1.6 kg/s is an adequate value to efficiently achieve a nominal cooling capacity of 4.5 kW under single-effect operation. In turn, a rate of 2.2 kg/s is needed to obtain 7 kW in the double-effect mode.

As for the dimensions of that absorber configuration, the following considerations must be taken into account. Assuming that injectors are set up in parallel configuration and that a free distance of about 0.03 m is recommended

between them, it can be said that installing 18 sprayers implies to have a 0.55 m-length absorption chamber. Besides, from experimental results given in [24], it can be drawn that the absorption chamber must be around 0.16 m-width. Regarding its depth, the only limitation is to Jet at least 0.2 m for the sheets to develop. Thus, the final volume of the absorption chamber is around 0.018 m^3 , which for a nominal chilling power of 7 kW yields a ratio of $2.5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3/\text{kW}$. As for the solution air-cooler, in the present case it consisted of two identical finned-tube heat exchangers installed in parallel circuits with a front area of 0.4 m^2 . Lastly, it is interesting to mention that the single-double-effect absorption machine including the present absorber design is 1 m-length, 0.8 m-width and 1.2 m-height, which yields a total volume of about 1 m^3 .

5. Simulation results for the selected absorber configuration

In order to simulate the behavior of the selected absorber configuration under different working conditions, a computational program was developed in *Matlab* following the mathematical model exposed in Section 3. Below, some of the most relevant results given by simulations are exposed and discussed.

5.1. Single-effect operation mode

In Table 1 one can find some of the numerical outcomes obtained when simulating the single-effect operation mode of the absorber under two different outdoor temperatures: $36 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which is a very common summer temperature not only in Madrid, but also in the Mediterranean coast; and $41 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which represents extreme working conditions, rarely reached in Spain. Notice that variables needed to run the program were taken from the simulation of the absorption cycle according to [30].

Firstly, it is interesting to notice that the higher is the outdoor temperature the lower is the absorption capacity. This is because at high ambient temperatures, the solution enters the absorber warmer and, consequently, its absorption potential decreases. Cornering the solution air-cooler, the simulation results showed that it may work with outlet solution temperatures of $1.5\text{-}2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ above the ambient air. This fact enables to reach subcooling rates of about $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for flat-fan sheets in the sprayer bank, which leads to a great absorption potential. In this sense, simulations showed that mean mass transfer coefficients of about $3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m/s}$ may be obtained.

It is notable that these results are consistent with those experimentally found by [24]. What is more, the values obtained for the approach to equilibrium factor are in excellent agreement with those given in that experimental work, about 0.90 for 200-mm- length sheets.

Table 1. Main simulation results for the absorber under single-effect operation mode.

Parameter	$T_{out} = 36 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$T_{out} = 41 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
$Q_{s,max}$ (kW)	4.4	3.8
Q_{abs} (kW)	4.9	4.3
T_9 ($^\circ\text{C}$)	38.3	43.3
T_7 ($^\circ\text{C}$)	37.8	42.8
$\dot{m}_{s,sheet}$ (kg/s)	2.78×10^{-2}	2.78×10^{-2}
$\Delta T_{sub,sheet}$ ($^\circ\text{C}$)	5.2	4.6
F_{sheet}	0.937	0.939
$\bar{h}_{m,sheet}$ (m/s)	3.09×10^{-4}	3.02×10^{-4}
$\dot{m}_{v,sheet}$ (kg/s)	9.42×10^{-5}	8.12×10^{-5}
$(T_f - T_i)_{sheet}$ ($^\circ\text{C}$)	4.9	4.3
$(X_i - X_f)_{sheet}$ (%)	2.6	2.2
$\dot{m}_{s,g}$ (kg/s)	2.03×10^{-2}	2.16×10^{-2}
$\Delta T_{sub,g}$ ($^\circ\text{C}$)	10.9	10.5
F_g	0.933	0.938
$\bar{h}_{m,g}$ (m/s)	2.29×10^{-4}	2.19×10^{-4}
$\dot{m}_{v,g}$ (kg)	1.31×10^{-4}	1.23×10^{-4}
$(T_f - T_i)_g$ ($^\circ\text{C}$)	10.2	9.9
$(X_i - X_f)_g$ (%)	5.0	4.7

On the other hand, it is interesting to underline the great absorption power of the solution sheet at the return of the generator. In fact, it is able to absorb a rate of vapor higher than sheets in the bank of sprayers. After the vapor absorption process, the solution flowing through the sprayer of the generator return is diluted by approximately 5%, while its temperature increases around $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. In turn, the LiBr concentration of the other solution sheets decreases about 2.5%, whereas the temperature rises between $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The fact of obtaining a greater increase in the solution temperature for the "generator sheet" is not only due to the higher rate of absorbed vapor, but also to the following reasons: firstly, the solution mass flow rate is lower in the "generator sheet"; secondly, the higher concentration of the solution yields higher specific absorption heat rates.

5.2. Double-effect operation mode

In Table 2, the simulation results corresponding to the absorber working in double-effect operation mode are shown for two ambient temperatures: 36 °C and 41 °C. As for the single-effect stage, it was noticed that absorption capacity decreases when outdoor temperature rises. Comparing with the single-effect operation mode, the solution flat-fan sheets of the bank are able to absorb a greater rate of vapor owing to the higher concentration of the solution. In turn, the absorption capacity of the solution sheets at the generator returns is considerably lower because of the higher solution temperatures.

Table 2. Main simulation results for the absorber under double-effect operation mode.

Parameter	$T_{o,air} = 36\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	$T_{o,air} = 41\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
$Q_{e,max}$ (kW)	6.9	5.8
Q_{abs} (kW)	7.6	6.1
T_g (°C)	37.8	43.0
T_7 (°C)	37.7	42.8
$\dot{m}_{v,sheet}$ (kg/s)	2.78×10^{-2}	2.78×10^{-2}
$\Delta T_{sub,sheet}$ (°C)	9.1	7.7
F_{sheet}	0.940	0.941
$\bar{h}_{m,sheet}$ (m/s)	2.99×10^{-4}	2.87×10^{-4}
$\dot{m}_{v,sheet}$ (kg/s)	1.60×10^{-4}	1.36×10^{-4}
$(T_f, T)_{sheet}$ (°C)	8.5	7.2
$(X_i, X_f)_{sheet}$ (%)	4.4	3.6
$\dot{m}_{v,HG}$ (kg/s)	1.43×10^{-2}	1.62×10^{-2}
$\bar{h}_{m,HG}$ (m/s)	1.02×10^{-4}	9.04×10^{-5}
$\dot{m}_{v,HG}$ (kg/s)	1.36×10^{-5}	1.09×10^{-5}
$\dot{m}_{v,LG}$ (kg/s)	1.11×10^{-2}	1.21×10^{-2}
$\bar{h}_{m,LG}$ (m/s)	1.64×10^{-4}	1.52×10^{-4}
$\dot{m}_{v,LG}$ (kg/s)	3.10×10^{-5}	2.03×10^{-5}

6. Experimental results: Validation of the model

In order to validate the absorber model, it was decided to run it with some experimental parameters as input variables, namely: pressure in the absorber, outdoor air temperature, mass flow rates in the solution air-cooler and solution conditions at the generators returns (temperature, concentration and mass flow rate. The objective is to compare experimentally measured values with simulation results for the same input variables.

The absorber testing facility consisted of a single-double-effect absorption prototype which has been recently designed and built by our research group. It is a directly air-cooled LiBr/H₂O absorption chiller which integrates both single- and double-effect cycles in the same unit. In the single-effect operation mode, it is driven by solar heat. In turn, the double-effect stage is fired by energy sources such as waste heat or any kind of fuel. Design cooling capacities are 4.5 kW and 7 kW, respectively. Note that the absorber installed in that prototype presented the configuration recommended in Section 4.3. For further details on the absorption prototype and the experimental procedure, the reader is referred to [26].

Data used for comparison were taken from several trials carried out during the experimental evaluation of that single-double-effect absorption prototype. Below, one can firstly find a comparison between predictions and measurements corresponding to the trial performed on 5 August 2010, taken as an illustrative example of the absorber behavior during a real day. Subsequently, a comparison for data collected during the whole experimental campaign of the prototype will be given.

6.1. Results for a specific trial: 5 August 2010

First of all, it is interesting to note that on 5 August 2010 the prototype was operated in single-effect mode, [26]. Fig. 12 shows the comparison made for the heat exchanged rate in the absorber air-cooler. The black line represents predicted values whereas the gray one represents experimentally obtained results. As seen, the agreement was quite good, especially in the central part of the experiment, when working conditions were closer to steady state conditions. It was found that about 85% of the measured data matched the simulation results with an error lower than $\pm 10\%$.

Solution temperature at the outlet of the absorber air-cooler (T_7) is the next parameter to be analyzed. Note that it corresponds to the solution temperature at the beginning of the flat-fan sheets in the bank of sprayers. Fig. 13 shows a notable concordance between predictions and measurements, being the difference lower than 4% for all the data. As in the previous comparison, a noticeably better agreement was observed in the central part of the experiment.

Fig. 12. Heat transfer rates in the solution air-cooler of the absorber.

Fig. 13. Temperatures at the beginning of the solution sheets.

In Fig. 14, the measured temperatures at the end of the solution sheets are compared against the corresponding results from simulations. In this case, it was observed that the absorber model tended to slightly underpredict the results. However, the mismatch was found to be within the 5% for almost all the measurements, which can be regarded as an evidence of the goodness of the absorption process modeling.

Fig. 14. Temperatures at the end of the solution sheet.

Fig. 15 shows the temperature differences between the outdoor air and the solution in the absorber reservoir, T_1 . As seen, an acceptable concordance was found between experimental and predicted values, being measured temperatures around 7% lower than predictions. Another noteworthy aspect drawn from Fig. 15 is that the absorber cooler was able to maintain the solution temperature just between 5 °C and 7 °C above the ambient temperature. This can be regarded as a relevant feature of the present absorber design since, owing to the low solution temperatures, absorption machines can work far from crystallization limits.

Last but not least, Fig. 16 compares the actual cooling power of the absorption prototype with the potential cooling capacity drawn from the absorber simulation. It is interesting to note that, while the gray line represents the effective cooling power obtained from measurements in the chilled water circulating through the prototype's evaporator, the black line indicates the maximum cooling capacity that could be reached with the absorption power of the sheets (taking into account that the vapor produced in the expansion valve does not produce cooling effect). In this case, it can be seen that the cooling power delivered in the evaporator was about 20% lower than the total capacity of the absorber. However, in the central part of the experiment the difference was reduced to 10-15%. To the authors' thought, the difference between $Q_{e,exp}$ and $Q_{e,pred}$ may be partially due to thermal losses in the prototype's evaporator. Nonetheless it is worth mentioning that, in order to reach the maximum capacity offered by the absorber, the prototype should be able to produce a certain amount of refrigerant that, likely, was not generated in the studied case owing to several factors concerning the operation of the whole prototype.

Fig. 15. Temperature differences between the solution in the absorber and the outdoor air.

Fig. 16. Comparison between measured and maximum cooling power.

6.2. Results for the overall experimental period

When considering all the test carried out with the single- double-effect absorption prototype (in both of its operation modes), the comparison of simulation and experimental results for the absorber can be summarized as follows. As regards to the heat power rate in the absorber air-cooler, around 80% of data were within $\pm 10\%$. As for the solution temperatures at the beginning and the end of the sheets, the mathematical model fitted quite well the measurements since the discrepancies were lower than 5% in any case. Regarding the temperature in the solution reservoir, the agreement between measurements and predictions was satisfactory as well, since the measured temperatures were 5-8% lower than predicted. Lastly, the measured cooling power in the evaporator of the prototype was about 20% lower than potential cooling capacity given by the absorber. As pointed out earlier, this fact seems to be due to thermal losses taking place in the evaporator and other components of the prototype.

On the other hand, it is worth mentioning that during the afore- mentioned experimental period, the prototype was operated under a wide range of working conditions (ambient temperatures from 25 °C to 40 °C) and no signs of solution crystallization were detected. What is more, the absorber design enabled to keep the final absorption temperature between 5 °C and 8 °C above the ambient temperature.

6.3. Experimental uncertainties

Following information given in [26] about the measurement system and according to [31], an experimental uncertainty analysis was performed. The mean results for the main parameters used in this study are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Experimental uncertainties.

Operation parameter	Uncertainty
Temperatures	± 0.1 °C
$Q_{ac,exp}$	$\pm 4.8\%$
$Q_{e,exp}$	$\pm 4.6\%$

7. Discussion

In this section, the above exposed results will be discussed from a physical point of view; that is, it will be seen how important is the performance of the proposed absorber design for the any air- cooled LiBr/H₂O machine to operate without crystallizing the solution.

As above mentioned, in absorption machines it is essential to have an effective cooling system that reduces the solution temperature after the vapor absorption process. Besides, the mass transfer coefficient in that process must be as higher as possible in order to minimize the circulating solution volume, which implies lower pumping consumptions and also reduced dimensions and weight. In this sense, adiabatic absorbers with flat-fan sheets seem to be one of the most adequate options for LiBr/H₂O air-cooled machines. The fact of facing heat and mass transfer separately enables to achieve greater performance in both process.

Regarding the solution cooling in the proposed absorber design, it was experimentally found that the solution in the absorber reservoir (absorption temperature) can be maintained between 5 °C and 7 °C above the ambient temperature (Fig. 15). This may be regarded as an important achievement in air-cooled systems, as seen for instance in [32]. Besides, it is interesting to underline the high posed system is able to effectively remove the absorption heat as it is generated, which is a key factor to obtain low absorption temperatures.

From a classical PTX diagram (or Dühring plot) for LiBr/H₂O solutions it can be drawn that the lower is the absorption temperature the further the crystallization conditions are; in other words, working with low absorption temperatures reduces the risk of solution crystallization for the same increment of solution concentration in the generator. Taking for instance one of the experiments performed with the aforementioned single-double effect machine [26] and representing the solution working conditions at an out- door temperature of 38.5 °C (Fig. 17), it can be seen that the absorber enabled the solution to work considerably far from the crystallization limits. Note that in the represented case the increment of the solution concentration in the generator was of 4%, while the solution temperature at the generator outlet was about 92 °C. Complementary, in [32] it was experimentally shown that this kind of absorbers permits air-cooled double-effect chillers to reliably work without solution crystallization at outdoor temperatures above 40 °C.

On the other hand, using flat-fan sheets in adiabatic absorbers allows not only for greater mass transfer coefficients, but also for higher transfer areas, as experimentally found by [24]. As a result, the volume of the absorption chamber can be significantly reduced in comparison with absorbers commonly installed in commercial machines. When analyzing for instance the 7-kW water-cooled absorption chiller *Yazaki WFC600S* [33], it is seen that it includes a falling film type absorption chamber that approximately occupies 0.05 m³. This yields a ratio of 7.2×10^{-3} m³ per

kW of chilling power, which is about three times greater than obtained for the absorber proposed in the present work. In this sense, it is interesting to highlight that achieving highly compact absorbers is generally considered as a very desirable feature in absorption machines since this is usually the biggest component in this kind of systems.

Lastly, it is worth mentioning that, as the pressure drop in the sprayers forming the flat-fan sheets is relatively low, the associated pumping consumption is quite small (see Fig. 7).

In view of the above distinguishing characteristics, it is possible to state that this new generation of absorbers significantly contributes to improvement of current absorption technology, especially when considering air-cooled absorption machines. Note that currently in the market there is not any commercial LiBr/H₂O absorption chiller directly cooled by air mainly because of two difficulties that might be overcome with the proposed absorber design: the difficulties in avoiding the solution crystallization and the great dimensions of the absorbers.

Fig. 17. Dühring diagram of the solution cycle working at ambient temperature of 38.5°C (test performed on 13/07/2010, Ref. [25]).

8. Conclusions

In the present work, a new design of direct air-cooled adiabatic absorbers with flat-fan sheets was presented and discussed. Like-wise, a mathematical model for analysis and simulation of this kind of absorbers was developed. Some experimental results of a specific adiabatic absorber operating in a LiBr/H₂O single-double effect air-cooled prototype were shown and compared with the corresponding simulation results to validate the model. Additionally, the configuration of that particular absorber was optimized in this paper.

It was concluded that an absorber configuration consisting of 18 flat-fan sheet injectors and an air flow rate of 1.6 kg/s is very adequate to provide a cooling capacity of 4.5 kW in single-effect operation mode. In turn, with the same number of sprayers and by increasing the air flow rate up to 2.2 kg/s, it was observed that a cooling capacity of 7 kW may be effectively achieved in double-effect operation mode.

The agreement between numerical and experimental results was found to be quite good. Actually, for all the characteristic temperatures in the absorber, the mismatch between measurements and predictions was under 10%, being around 4–5% in most cases. In turn, when considering the heat transfer rate in the absorber air-cooler, it was found that about 80% of the data were within an error band of $\pm 10\%$. On those grounds, it can be concluded that the proposed model is valid to perform numerical simulations of air-cooled adiabatic absorbers with LiBr/H₂O flat-fan sheets. Nevertheless, improvements are still needed to achieve better predictions of the absorber performance.

On the other hand, it was observed that the actual cooling power delivered in the prototype's evaporator was around

20% lower than the maximum cooling capacity offered by the absorber. The main reason for that seems to be the fact that the prototype produced less water vapor than could be absorbed by the solution sheets in the absorber. As a result, further investigation on the prototype operation is recommended to make the most of the absorber capacity.

Finally, it is remarkable that the proposed absorber allows working with such low solution temperatures that crystallization problems are avoided. As far as we know, there is not any absorber with similar characteristics neither in the market nor in the scientific literature.

Nomenclature

A	area (m ²)	<i>Subscripts</i>	
c_p	isobaric specific heat (kJ/kg K)	a	absorber
F	approach to equilibrium factor	abs	absorption
HG	high-pressure generator	ac	air-cooler of the absorber
h	specific enthalpy (kJ/kg)	air	air flow
h_{abs}	specific heat of absorption (kJ/kg)	b	bulk conditions
h_m	mean mass transfer coefficient (m/s)	$bank$	bank of sprayers in the absorber
LG	low-pressure generator	e	evaporator/evaporation
$m_$	mass flow rate (kg/s)	eq	equilibrium conditions
Q	heat transfer rate (kW)	exp	experimental
RSP	recirculation solution pump	f	final position in a flat-fan sheet
SP	solution pump	fan	fan of the absorber air-cooler
T	temperature (K)	g	single-effect generator
t	time (s)	HG	high-pressure generator
U	global heat transfer coefficient (W/m ² K)	i	inlet/initial position in a flat-fan sheet
W	power consumption (kW)	LG	low-pressure generator
X	concentration of LiBr in the solution (%)	o	outlet
		out	outdoors air

Greek symbols

ΔP	pressure drop (Pa)
ΔT_{sub}	initial subcooling of the solution sheet flow (°C)
ΔX	increment in the solution mass fraction (%)
ΔX_{lm}	logarithmic mean mass fraction difference
η	efficiency
ρ	density
θ	aperture angle of the sheet (°)

Acknowledgements

This research work was subsidized by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation under research projects PSE INVISIO (sub- project SP3) and ENE2010-20650-CO2-01. The authors wish to thank Emilio Martín, R&D technician, for his willing and enthusiastic contribution to the study. A. Gonzalez-Gil would like to thank CSIC for the financial support of his PhD.

References

- [1] Torrella E, Sánchez D, Cabello R, Larumbe JA, Llopis R. On-site real-time evaluation of an air-conditioning direct-fired double-effect absorption chiller. *Appl Energ* 2009;86:968–75.
- [2] Somers C, Mortazavi A, Hwang Y, Radermacher R, Rodgers P, Al-Hashimi S. Modeling water/lithium bromide absorption chillers in ASPEN Plus. *Appl Energ* 2011;88:4197–205.
- [3] Kim DS, Infante-Ferreira CA. Solar refrigeration options-a state-of-the-art review. *Int J Refrig* 2008;31:3–15.
- [4] Izquierdo M, Lizarte R, Marcos JD, Gutiérrez G. Air conditioning using an air-cooled single effect lithium bromide absorption chiller: results of a trial conducted in Madrid in August 2005. *Appl Therm Eng* 2008;28:1074–81.
- [5] Monné C, Alonso S, Palacín F, Serra L. Monitoring and simulation of an existing solar powered absorption cooling system in Zaragoza (Spain). *Appl Therm Eng* 2011;31:28–35.

- [6] Ziegler F. State of the art in sorption heat pumping and cooling technologies. *Int J Refrig* 2002;25:450–9.
- [7] Gluesenkamp K, Radermacher R, Hwang. Trends in absorption machines. In: *Proceedings of the international sorption heat pump conference (ISHPC11)*, Padua (Italy); 2011. p. 13–22.
- [8] Izquierdo M, Venegas M, Rodríguez P, Lecuona A. Crystallization as a limit to develop solar air-cooled LiBr-H₂O absorption systems using low-grade heat. *Sol Energ Mat Sol C* 2004;81:205–16.
- [9] Herold KE, Radermacher R, Klein SA. *Absorption chillers and heat pumps*. CRC Press; 1996.
- [10] Lee H, Koo K, Jeon S, Kim JS, Lee H, Oh YS, et al. Thermodynamic design data and performance evaluation of the water + lithium bromide + lithium iodide + lithium nitrate + lithium chloride system for absorption chiller. *Appl Therm Eng* 2000;20:707–20.
- [11] Kim JS, Park Y, Lee H. Performance evaluation of absorption chiller using LiBr + H₂N(CH₂)₂OH + H₂O, LiBr + HO(CH₂)₃OH + H₂O, and LiBr + (HOCH₂CH₂)₂NH + H₂O as working fluids. *Appl Therm Eng* 1999;19:217–25.
- [12] Bourouis M, Vallès M, Medrano M, Coronas A. Absorption of water vapour in the falling film of water- (LiBr + LiI + LiNO₃ + LiCl) in a vertical tube at air-cooling thermal conditions. *Int J Therm Sci* 2005;44:491–8.
- [13] Jian S, Lin F, Shigang Z. Performance calculation of single effect absorption heat pump using LiBr + LiNO₃ + H₂O as working fluid. *Appl Therm Eng* 2010;30:2680–4.
- [14] Medrano M, Bourouis M, Coronas A. Absorption of water vapour in the falling film of water-lithium bromide inside a vertical tube at air-cooling thermal conditions. *Int J Therm Sci* 2002;41:891–8.
- [15] Castro J, Oliva A, Perez-Segarra CD, Oliet C. Modelling of the heat exchangers of a small capacity, hot water driven, air-cooled H₂O-LiBr absorption cooling machine. *Int J Refrig* 2008;31:75–86.
- [16] Liao X, Radermacher R. Absorption chiller crystallization control strategies for integrated cooling heating and power systems. *Int J Refrig* 2007;30:904–11.
- [17] Kim DS, Infante-Ferreira CA. Air-cooled LiBr-water absorption chillers for solar air conditioning in extremely hot weathers. *Energ Convers Manage* 2009;50:1018–25.
- [18] Ali AHH. Design of a compact absorber with a hydrophobic membrane contactor at the liquid-vapor interface for lithium bromide-water absorption chillers. *Appl Energ* 2010;87:1112–21.
- [19] Wang L, Chen GM, Wang Q, Zhong M. Thermodynamic performance analysis of gas-fired air-cooled adiabatic absorption refrigeration systems. *Appl Therm Eng* 2007;27:1642–52.
- [20] Ryan WA. Water absorption in an adiabatic spray of aqueous lithium bromide solution. In: *Proceedings of the international absorption heat pump conference*. ASME; 1993. p. 155–62.
- [21] Warnakulasuriya FSK, Worekx MM. Drop formation of swirl-jet nozzles with high viscous solution in vacuum-new absorbent in spray absorption refrigeration. *Int J Heat Mass Transfer* 2008;51:3362–8.
- [22] Arzoz D, Rodriguez P, Izquierdo M. Experimental study on the adiabatic absorption of water vapor into LiBr-H₂O solutions. *Appl Therm Eng* 2005;25:797–811.
- [23] Palacios E, Izquierdo M, Lizarte R, Marcos JD. Lithium bromide absorption machines: pressure drop and mass transfer in solutions conical sheets. *Energ Convers Manage* 2009;50:1802–9.
- [24] Palacios E, Izquierdo M, Marcos JD, Lizarte R. Evaluation of mass absorption in LiBr flat-fan sheets. *Appl Energ* 2009;86:2574–82.
- [25] Izquierdo M, Martín E, Palacios E. Absorber and absorber-evaporator assembly for absorption machines and lithium bromide-water absorption machines that integrate said absorber and absorber-evaporator assembly. Patent EP1641.448; 2011.
- [26] González-Gil A, Izquierdo M, Marcos JD, Palacios E. Experimental evaluation of a direct air-cooled lithium bromide-water absorption prototype for solar air conditioning. *Appl Therm Eng* 2011;31:3358–68.
- [27] Acosta-Iborra A, García N, Santana D. Modelling non-isothermal absorption of vapour into expanding liquid sheets. *Int J Heat Mass Transfer* 2009;52:3042–54.
- [28] Incropera FK, De Witt DP. *Fundamentos de transferencia de calor*. 4th ed. México: Prentice hall; 1999.
- [29] Kays WM, London AL. *Compact heat exchangers*. 3rd ed. New York: McGraw- Hill; 1984.
- [30] Marcos JD, Izquierdo M, Palacios E. New method for COP optimization in water- and air-cooled single

- and double effect LiBr/water absorption machines. *Int J Refrig* 2011;34:1348–59.
- [31] Kline SJ, McClintock FA. Describing uncertainties in single-sample experiments. *Mech Eng* 1953;75:3–8.
- [32] Izquierdo M, Marcos JD, Palacios ME, González-Gil A. Experimental evaluation of a low-power direct air-cooled double effect LiBr-H₂O absorption prototype. *Energy* 2012;37:737–48.
- [33] Izquierdo M, Hernández F, Martín E. Solar cooling in Madrid: energetic efficiencies. *Sol Energy* 1997;60:367–77.